

RADx Data Hub: Study Registration Processes

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RADx RAD Data Management Overview

RADx RAD Data Management Overview

WHO

- RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS PROTECTIONS

WHAT

- RESEARCH PARTICIPANT PROTECTIONS
- BROAD DATA SHARING

HOW

- STUDY REGISTRATION
 - INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION
 - DATA SHARING/SUBMISSION INFORMATION

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

OMB Control Number: 0925-0670
Expiration Date: November 30, 2022

Clear Form

Rapid Acceleration for Diagnostics Program (RADx) Institutional Certification*

For studies using data generated for the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics Program (RADx)

Date: 02/02/2021

Name of RADx Program Admin:

NIH, HHS 9000 Rockville Pike Bethesda, MD 20892-7395

Re: Institutional Certification of [NAME OF INSTITUTION] to Accompany
Submission of the Dataset from [ORIGINAL STUDY NAME] for
 [PROJECT TITLE FOR DATA TO BE SUBMITTED]
to an NIH-designated data repository.

Dear

The submission of data to the NIH-designated data repository is being made with institutional approval from _____, along with appropriate institutional approvals from collaborating sites, as listed here:

[IF APPLICABLE ENTER COLLABORATING SITE NAMES HERE AND CLICK 'ADD TO LIST']

LIST OF COLLABORATING SITES

Add to list >>

Clear list

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

- RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS PROTECTIONS
- GENERAL RESEARCH USE (GRU)

DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- DATA
- ACKNOWLEDGEMENT STATEMENT
- STUDY DESCRIPTION

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The _____ hereby assures that submission of data from the study entitled _____ to an NIH-designated data repository meets the following expectations:

- *• The data submission is consistent, as appropriate, with applicable national, tribal, and state laws and regulations as well as relevant institutional policies.
- *• Any limitations on the research use of the data, as expressed in the informed consent documents, are delineated in the table on page 3.
- *• The identities of research participants will not be disclosed to NIH-designated data repositories.
- *• An Institutional Review Board (IRB), and/or Privacy Board, and/or equivalent body, and a relevant senior-level institutional staff (e.g., Dean, Vice President/Provost for Research, Chief Science Officer) as applicable, has reviewed the investigator's proposal for data submission and assures that:
 - *○ The protocol for the collection of genomic and phenotypic data is consistent with 45 CFR Part 46;²
 - *○ Data submission and subsequent data sharing for research purposes are consistent with the informed consent of study participants from whom the data were obtained;
 - *○ Consideration was given to risks to individual participants and their families associated with data submitted to NIH-designated data repositories and subsequent sharing, including unrestricted access to genomic summary results;
 - *○ To the extent relevant and possible, consideration was given to risks to groups or populations associated with submitting data to NIH-designated data repositories and subsequent sharing, including unrestricted access to genomic summary results; and
 - *○ The investigator's plan for de-identifying datasets is consistent with the HHS Regulations for the Protection of Human Subjects**

* Certification must be provided for all sites contributing samples. If more than one site is contributing samples, the primary site may submit one Institutional Certification indicating that they are providing certification on behalf of all collaborating sites. Alternatively, each site providing samples may provide its own Institutional Certification.

**Investigators should de-identify human data that they submit to NIH-designated data repositories according to the standards set forth in the HHS Regulations for the Protection of Human Subjects to ensure that the identities of research subjects cannot be readily ascertained with the data. Investigators should also strip the data of identifiers according to the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Privacy Rule. The de-identified data should be assigned random, unique codes by the investigator, and the key to other study identifiers held by the submitting institution.

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The individual-level data are to be made available through (check one)

controlled-access ³

unrestricted access ⁴

If unrestricted access is marked, the data use limitations table on the following page(s) does not need to be completed.

* Certification must be provided for all sites contributing samples. If more than one site is contributing samples, the primary site may submit one Institutional Certification indicating that they are providing certification on behalf of all collaborating sites. Alternatively, each site providing samples may provide its own Institutional Certification.

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NIH expects the submitting institution(s) to select one of the three standard [Data Use Limitations](#) (DULs) for appropriate secondary use, or, if necessary, create a customized DUL. DULs are developed based on the original informed consent of the participant(s).

Data Use Limitations

General Research Use	GRU	Use of the data is limited only by the terms of the Data Use Certification: these data will be added to the dbGaP Collection .
Health/Medical/Biomedical	HMB	Use of the data is limited to health/medical/biomedical purposes, does not include the study of population origins or ancestry.
Disease-specific [list disease]	DS	Use of the data must be related to the specified disease.
Other		[ENTER CUSTOMIZED TEXT, IF APPLICABLE]

Additional modifiers to the standard DULs (e.g., Not-for-profit Use Only) can be indicated, if appropriate. Use of the modifiers should have a basis in the informed consent from the participants or in special knowledge of the preferences of the original study population.

Data Use Limitation Modifiers (Optional)

IRB Approval Required	IRB	Requestor must provide documentation of local IRB approval.
Publication Required	PUB	Requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community.
Collaboration Required	COL	Requestor must provide a letter of collaboration with the primary study investigator(s).
Not-for-profit Use Only	NPU	Use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations.
Methods	MDS	Use of the data includes methods development research (e.g., development and testing of software or algorithms).
Genetic Studies Only	GSO	Use of the data is limited to genetic studies only.

Using the tables above, please indicate in the table below the consent group(s) for each collaborating study site. Use one row per consent group.

Collaborating Site Name	Data Use Limitation	Data Use Limitation Modifiers (optional)
Eg: Cold Cohort Study	Health/Medical/Biomedical	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>
Eg: Cold Cohort Study	Disease-specific Research [list disease]	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>
	General Research Use	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>
	Select consent group title	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>
	Select consent group title	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>
	Select consent group title	IRB <input type="checkbox"/> PUB <input type="checkbox"/> COL <input type="checkbox"/> NPU <input type="checkbox"/> MDS <input type="checkbox"/> GSO <input type="checkbox"/>

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

- RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS PROTECTIONS
- GENERAL RESEARCH USE (GRU)**

DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- DATA
- ACKNOWLEDGEMENT STATEMENT
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DATA SUBMISSION INFORMATION

Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics (RADxSM) Data Sharing & Submission Information

Version 12/2020

Provide the information listed below and return to your NIH Program Officer (PO).

Checklist of required documents:

[Institutional Certifications](#)

RADxSM Data Sharing & Submission Information

PART I – Study Registration Information

Study name:

Is this a multi-center study?

Yes No

If YES, list participating sites:

Data will be submitted (choose one):

By date (MM/DD/YYYY)

Data will be submitted by batches over Study Timeline

(e.g. based on clinical trial enrollment benchmarks)

Specify:

Target data delivery date: (MM/DD/YYYY) Target public release date: (MM/DD/YYYY)

Number of gigabytes of data to be deposited: Estimated number of study participants:

The data are to be made available through:

Unrestricted access Controlled Access

RADxSM Data Hub

Sequence Read Archive (SRA)

Array Express

ClinVar

dbGaP

dbVar

dbSNP

ENA

GenBank

GEO

MGI

Trace Archive

Other (list all):

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DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- **DATA: WHEN/WHERE**
- ACKNOWLEDGEMENT STATEMENT
- STUDY DESCRIPTION

DATA SUBMISSION INFORMATION

PART IV – Study Description			
Study type(s) (e.g. collection, longitudinal, case-control, case set, control set, parent-offspring trios, cohort):			
Check all data types expected for this study:			
Species <input type="checkbox"/> Human Data <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Human Data	General Data Types <input type="checkbox"/> Behavioral <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical <input type="checkbox"/> Cognitive <input type="checkbox"/> Electronic Medical Records <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental (Physical) <input type="checkbox"/> Family History <input type="checkbox"/> Genomic <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):		
Sample Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Existing (Legacy) <input type="checkbox"/> Prospective Sample	<input type="checkbox"/> Genotyping <input type="checkbox"/> Imaging <input type="checkbox"/> Immunological <input type="checkbox"/> Individual Genotype <input type="checkbox"/> Individual Phenotype <input type="checkbox"/> Individual Sequencing <input type="checkbox"/> Metabolic <input type="checkbox"/> Metagenomic	<input type="checkbox"/> Physical Activity <input type="checkbox"/> Proteomic <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological <input type="checkbox"/> Questionnaires/Surveys <input type="checkbox"/> Social <input type="checkbox"/> Supporting Documents	
Genomic <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregate Data <input type="checkbox"/> Individual-level Data <input type="checkbox"/> Non-human Data <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):			
Phenotype <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregate Data <input type="checkbox"/> Individual-level Data <input type="checkbox"/> Non-human Data <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):			
Sample Types <input type="checkbox"/> DNA <input type="checkbox"/> From Repository Name: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> Germline <input type="checkbox"/> Microbiome <input type="checkbox"/> Mitochondria <input type="checkbox"/> RNA <input type="checkbox"/> Single Cell <input type="checkbox"/> Tumor/Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):			
Genomic Data Types			
Genotype <input type="checkbox"/> Array CGH CNVs <input type="checkbox"/> Array-derived Genotypes <input type="checkbox"/> CNV calls derived from Sequencing <input type="checkbox"/> CNV calls from microarray <input type="checkbox"/> Genotype calls derived from Sequence <input type="checkbox"/> Non-human data <input type="checkbox"/> Somatic SNV (.MAF) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	Sequencing <input type="checkbox"/> 16S rRNA <input type="checkbox"/> Epigenomic Marks <input type="checkbox"/> Sanger <input type="checkbox"/> Targeted Exome <input type="checkbox"/> Targeted Genome <input type="checkbox"/> Targeted Transcriptome <input type="checkbox"/> Whole Exome <input type="checkbox"/> Whole Genome <input type="checkbox"/> Whole Transcriptome <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	Analyses <input type="checkbox"/> Array-derived Expression <input type="checkbox"/> Array-derived Methylation <input type="checkbox"/> Association/Linkage Results <input type="checkbox"/> RNA Seq derived Expression <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	Array Data <input type="checkbox"/> Expression Array <input type="checkbox"/> Methylation Array <input type="checkbox"/> SNP Array <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

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DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- DATA: WHAT
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DATA SUBMISSION INFORMATION

PART V - Acknowledgement Statement(s)***

The submitting PI should provide specific points that should be included in an acknowledgement, such as sources of support or collaborators who have made subjects or samples available. Any NIH support must be specifically acknowledged by including the grant number. Consider citing a specific publication that comprehensively describes the origin of the dataset.

The suggested Acknowledgement Statement to accompany the dataset is:

EXAMPLE:

[ANY PROGRAM SPECIFIC LANGUAGE]. National Institutes of Health (NIH) support was provided in part by grants from [Institute or Center Name]. [Grant pr contract #]. The dataset(s) used for the analyses described in this manuscript was obtained from [NAME OF REPOSITORY] found at [https://\[XXXXXX\]](https://[XXXXXX]) number phs00XXXX

PART VI - Original Summary of Study

Provide an original description of the study.¹

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

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DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- DATA: WHAT
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DATA SUBMISSION INFORMATION

dbGaP
GENOTYPES and PHENOTYPES

National Institutes of Health The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)
dbGaP Study Accession: phs000178.v11.p8

Request Access

Study version history

Study | Phenotype Datasets | Variables | Molecular Datasets | Analyses | Documents

Jump to: [Authorized Access](#) | [Attribution](#) | [Authorized Requests](#)

Substudies

phs000854.v3.p8 : [Genome-Wide Analysis of Noncoding Regulatory Mutations in Cancer](#)

Study Description

The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) is a comprehensive and coordinated effort to accelerate our understanding of the molecular basis of cancer through the application of genome analysis technologies, including large-scale genome sequencing. TCGA is a joint effort of the National Cancer Institute (NCI) and the National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI), which are both part of the National Institutes of Health, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.

TCGA projects are organized by cancer type or subtype. Click [here](#) for a current list of cancer types selected for study in TCGA.

Data from TCGA (e.g., gene expression, copy number variation and clinical information), are available via the [Genomic Data Commons \(GDC\)](#).

Data from TCGA projects are organized into two tiers: **Open Access and Controlled Access.**

- Open Access data tier contains data that cannot be attributed to an individual research participant. The Open Access data tier does not require user certification. Data in Open Access tier are available in the TCGA Data Portal.
- Controlled Access data tier contains individual-level genotype data that are unique to an individual. Access to data in the Controlled Access data tier requires user certification through [dbGaP Authorized Access](#).

Important Links and Information

- As of June, 2016, primary TCGA data is available at [NCI Genomic Data Commons](#). Some data files derived from TCGA controlled-access data that are not part of the official TCGA dataset may be hosted at dbGaP.
- Request access via [Authorized Access](#)
 - [Instructions](#) for requestors
 - [Data Use Certification \(DUC\) Agreement](#)
- [Talking Glossary of Genetic Terms](#)

Provide an original description of the study!¹

INSTITUTIONAL CERTIFICATION

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DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

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PART VII - Consent Groups

The NIH promotes the broad and responsible sharing of research for 'general research use'. However, NIH also recognizes that in some circumstances broad sharing may not be consistent with the informed consent of the research participants whose data are included in the dataset. A data use limitation (DUL) statement is a brief written description of limitations, if any, on the distribution and use of human data submitted to controlled-access NIH designated data repositories, such as the NIH database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP). Limitations on the data use should be described in the [Institutional Certification](#). NIH provides [Points to Consider in Developing Effective Data Use Limitations](#) that are developed based on the original informed consent from the participants.

Data contains: Controlled Access Data Public Access Data

If your data does NOT contain Controlled Access Data, skip to Part IX.

If your data does contain Controlled Access Data, select all relevant consent group categories:

Consent Group Category	Data Use Limitations
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> General Research Use	Use of the data is limited only by the terms of the Data Use Certification (DUC)
<input type="checkbox"/> IRB approval required	Requestor must provide documentation of local IRB approval
<input type="checkbox"/> Publication required	Requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration required	Requestor must provide letter of collaboration with the primary study investigator(s)
<input type="checkbox"/> Not-for-profit use only	Use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations
<input type="checkbox"/> Health/Medical/Biomedical	Use of the data is limited to health/medical/biomedical purposes, does not include study of population origins or ancestry
<input type="checkbox"/> IRB approval required	Requestor must provide documentation of local IRB approval
<input type="checkbox"/> Publication required	Requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration required	Requestor must provide letter of collaboration with the primary study investigator(s)
<input type="checkbox"/> Not-for-profit use only	Use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations
<input type="checkbox"/> Disease-Specific	Use of the data must be related to the specified disease
<input type="checkbox"/> IRB approval required	Requestor must provide documentation of local IRB approval
<input type="checkbox"/> Publication required	Requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration required	Requestor must provide letter of collaboration with the primary study investigator(s)
<input type="checkbox"/> Not-for-profit use only	Use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations
<input type="checkbox"/> Related conditions	Use of data includes disease XX and related conditions (Describe and include examples):

Other (describe):

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DATA SHARING AND SUBMISSION INFORMATION

- DATA: ACKNOWLEDGEMENT STATEMENT
- STUDY DESCRIPTION

**FOR RADx
STUDY REGISTRATION
AND
DATA ACCESS
QUESTIONS AND
ASSISTANCE**

Vivian OTA WANG
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**NATIONAL
CANCER
INSTITUTE**

www.cancer.gov

www.cancer.gov/espanol